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Using information and communication technologies to improve efficiency in the tourism industry

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Abstract: The role of information and communication technologies is growing in all areas. Tourism is no exception, and its efficiency and competitiveness directly depend on such technologies. Online booking, mobile apps, virtual and augmented reality, artificial intelligence and big data are improving customer service and making travel services more accessible and personalized

Keywords: tourism market; development efficiency; online booking; virtual guides; artificial intelligence and chatbots; virtual reality; smart devices

Использование информационно-коммуникационных технологий для повышения эффективности в индустрии туризма

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Аннотация: Роль информационно-коммуникационных технологий возрастает по всем направлениям. Туризм не является исключением, и от таких технологий напрямую зависит его эффективность и конкурентоспособность. Онлайн-бронирование, мобильные приложения, виртуальная и дополненная реальность, искусственный интеллект и большие данные улучшают качество обслуживания клиентов и делают туристические услуги более доступными и персонализированными

Ключевые слова: туристический рынок; эффективность разработки; онлайн-бронирование; виртуальные гиды; искусственный интеллект и чат-боты; виртуальная реальность; умные устройства

Turizm industriyasini samaradorligini oshirishda axborot-kommunikatsion texnologiyalardan foydalanish

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Annotatsiya: Barcha sohalarda axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalarining roli ortib bormoqda. Turizm ham bundan mustasno emas, uning samaradorligi va raqobatbardoshligi bevosita ana shunday texnologiyalarga bog‘liq. Onlayn bron qilish, mobil ilovalar, virtual va kengaytirilgan reallik, sun‘iy intellekt va katta ma‘lumotlar mijozlar tajribasini yaxshilaydi va sayohat xizmatlarini yanada qulayroq va moslashtirilgan qiladi. Maqolada turistlarni jalb qilish, ularga xizmat ko‘rsatish xarajatlarini kamaytirish

Kalit so‘zlar: turistik bozor; rivojlanish samaradorligi; onlayn bron qilish; virtual qo‘llanmalar; sun‘iy intellekt va chatbotlar; virtual haqiqat; aqlli qurilmalar

Introduction.

Now tourism is not only a branch of the economy, it is socio-economic development and increasing cultural ties. The tourism business is actively developing and becoming especially relevant. The management mechanisms currently used improve the quality of services, target direction and optimize costs. And modern information and communication technologies significantly improve interaction with customers, increase accessibility and mobility. In the tourism business itself, many new opportunities have appeared that did not exist before. This includes online booking, virtual and augmented reality applications. Using these applications, there are many opportunities to learn about different countries, their culture and attractions.

Many works are devoted to the development of the tourism industry. The authors note that without a clear strategy it is impossible to achieve high results in tourism. Strategies must take into account local characteristics, tourist needs and changes in the market.

Research shows that digitalization makes it possible to optimize the work of tourism organizations. In the work of Alimova M.T. and Rakhmonov Sh.Sh. It has been noted that the use of new technologies for the tourism industry helps reduce personnel costs and improve interaction with customers [1]. Databases and analytical tools are becoming important for decision making in tourism. In the work of Vasilyeva L.V. The uniqueness of data analysis is proposed to identify tourist flows and forecast

them. Data implementation technologies can improve planning accuracy and improve management [2]. Many authors note the use of analytical platforms and CRM systems in marketing, which makes it possible to develop personalized offers and increase attractiveness to customers. Models based on artificial intelligence and chatbots have become widely used to improve the level of service and quickly respond to tourist requests. Most of the work is related to the fact that the introduction of such technologies in the tourism sector opens up opportunities for improving interaction with clients, increasing efficiency, accessibility of services and, as a result, increasing the competitiveness of regions and countries [3].

Solution methods.

Nowadays, tourism is developing dynamically and is a highly profitable sector of the world economy. By successfully developing tourism, such important sectors of the economy as transport and communications begin to develop. All this has a significant impact on trade and construction. In Uzbekistan, there are such favorable conditions for the development of tourism as climate, nature, and a large number of historical attractions. Nowadays, tourist services are organized in accordance with international standards [4]. The tourism industry is developing dynamically throughout the world. Recently, significant changes have occurred in this area. New modern information technologies began to be introduced into the field, and many new, interesting digital solutions appeared. Therefore, tourism is an area of rapidly growing application of information technology [5]. Such technologies used in tourism consist of various reservation systems, teleconferencing systems, video systems, management systems, airline electronic information systems, electronic money transfer, mobile networks, etc. Modern information technologies make it possible to transform the tourism industry, using many solutions that improve customer experience, optimize management and increase the competitiveness of companies [6]. Solutions that are most widespread in the tourism industry:

Online booking and event platforms - Platforms such as Booking.com, Airbnb and Expedia allow tourists to book accommodation, transport and excursions online. These platforms provide convenient interfaces for searching and comparing offers, and also ensure transaction security [7]. Additionally, mobile apps make the booking process even more convenient. Users can book a hotel room or buy a plane ticket directly from their smartphone, anywhere in the world.

Mobile applications and virtual guides which help users plan routes, visit interesting attractions and learn about them in a convenient format. Some provide offline support, making them especially important in remote locations without Internet connections. Data management systems and big data analytics - travel companies and

platforms use big data to study customer preferences, analyze weather and forecast trends.

This allows businesses to better segment their audience, tailor offers and adjust their marketing strategies [8]. For example, machine learning-based recommendation systems analyze users' purchase history and search queries to suggest suitable accommodations, itineraries and excursions. This allows you to increase conversion and improve customer satisfaction [9].

Use of artificial intelligence and chatbots - AI solutions and chatbots provide consultations in the shortest possible time and answer tourists' questions. Chatbots work around the clock, which is especially important for international companies serving customers from different time zones.

Virtual and augmented reality (VR and AR) - used to create virtual tours of attractions and hotels, as well as for interactivity. They allow users to “visit” a location or hotel before viewing a trip, which helps them better understand the atmosphere and conditions.

Blockchain technology can significantly simplify the processes of booking and paying for services, increase the transparency of transactions and reduce the risks of fraud [10]. Smart devices and Internet of things - smart devices such as smart switches for hotel rooms, lighting and temperature control systems, air conditioning - control security, simplify the stay of tourists and make their stay more comfortable. Biometrics and contactless payments - the use of biometric data to identify passengers and hotel customers speeds up the check-in process and increases the level of security [11].

Robots and automation are already being used in some hotels to perform routine tasks such as cleaning rooms or delivering food. Geolocation technologies such as GPS and Google Maps have become essential tools for travelers. Many travel companies use geolocation to create interactive maps and guides.

The latest technical means can significantly expand the exhibitor's capabilities in displaying exhibits, providing additional text and graphic information on a subject or era, showing missing exhibits, and organizing virtual exhibitions [12]. And the possibilities of kiosks are not limited to this. The leaders in the number of installations and the most original use of such kiosks are the USA and Thailand. Almost all museums in Thailand have installed touch kiosks to serve visitors. These are the Museum of History and Science (Texas), the American Museum of Natural History, the Museum of Science and High Technology and many others.

Results.

Technology is rapidly changing the travel industry, offering new opportunities for travelers, travel companies and other market participants.

Figure 1. Number of foreign tourists in the Republic of Uzbekistan

Using the example of our Republic, one can see an increase in the number of foreign citizens who arrived in the Republic of Uzbekistan for tourism purposes (Fig. 1). So in 2020, 1.4 million people visited the Republic, in 2021 - 1.1 million people, in 2022 - 3.6 million people, in 2023 - 4.9 million people, in 2024 (until September) - 5.7 million people.

Information technology in tourism continues to grow rapidly, and this process provides many indicators that illustrate its impact on the tourism industry.

Thus, online bookings account for more than 63% of all tourist orders, with about 83% of tourists booking their trips independently via the Internet (according to Statista). The online market is predicted to reach \$833 billion by 2025. These data reflect the growing popularity of digital travel platforms and services. The growth in global spending on mobile travel apps reached \$11 billion in 2023, and this figure could grow to \$17 billion by 2027.

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